

A Critical Analysis of Interference Induced Particle Wave Theory

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Abstract

We will focus mainly on the fundamental principles of wave-particle-duality in the interference induced particle-wave theory [1], ignoring any mathematical errors present (such as the addition of classical action to calculate the total energy of a parent wave) in its calculations. We will show how the theory, due to describing superposition states of particles using classical waves, disagrees with experimental observations of single-slit interferences.

Theory

"Every time a Parent Wave generates a new wave, the Parent Wave's energy level gets reduced by the amount of energy the newly generated wave gets."

"Whenever a wave depletes energy, it keeps depleting it till it reaches a 'threshold'. That's when it gets converted into a particle."

This is how the observation of particles with well defined positions is explained despite the wave-like behaviour of the same particle when unobserved.

The hypothesis assumes well defined energy values for the parent waves themselves. Assuming energy remains conserved (as assumed in the paper) the energy of the successive waves generated all added together should give the energy of the parent wave,

$$E_{\Psi_0} = NE_{\psi} \quad (1)$$

where Ψ is being used to denote the parent wave, ψ to denote the first successive waves generate and the result follows from the symmetry of the situation and energy conservation. The use of energy conservation is justified due to the waves being of classical nature, thus the system follows Noether's theorem.

When a measurement is made however, the "particle" is observed where the parent wave stops generating successive waves. As the hypothesis relies on real waves in space, that stop generating new waves when a measurement apparatus

disturbs the system, the position of the particle in case if an energy measurement instead should also be determined where the parent wave stops generating new waves, while the energy remaining to the parent wave should be found. This energy itself has to be well defined given by

$$E_{\Psi} = E_{\Psi_0} - nE_{\psi} \quad (2)$$

where the left hand side terms denotes the energy of the parent wave found in measurement, the first terms on RHS denotes the total initial energy of the parent wave(eq 1), and the second term on the RHS denotes the energy depleted to successive waves.

This well defined energy corresponds to a well defined momentum given non-relativistically by,

$$E_{\Psi} = \frac{p_{\Psi}^2}{2m} \text{ or } p_{\Psi} = \sqrt{2mE_{\Psi}} \quad (3)$$

Conclusion

Thus, a measurement on momentum should also give a well defined value given by the above equation. However, experimentally, whenever a measurement on position is made, the momentum is shown to distribute over a wide range of values as in a "single" slit experiment. When the position of an electron is calculated, the electron distributes widely over the screen in front which can be explained in standard QM using the uncertainty principle. In this hypothesis, however, the position measurement leads to a well defined momentum due to which the uncertainty principle can't be used to explain this phenomenon. As the hypothesis may suggest, the number of successive waves produced after the measurement interfere to produce the pattern on the screen, however, a position measurement as per the hypothesis causes the energy to dissipate to the energy threshold thus the wave now cannot carry enough energy to generate enough waves that can constructively produce the patterns on the screen as seen in the experiments.

Thus, the hypothesis can be rejected due to inconsistencies with experimental observations in the single slit experiment which standard QM explains with its uncertainty principle

References

- [1] Diggaj Jain. Interference-induced particle-wave theory, 2024.